

Striving for a sustainable surveillance of Ciguatera Poisoning in the Pacific: the Ciguawatch initiative

The South Pacific region is a well known historical hotspot for Ciguatera Poisoning (CP) [1], with the first poisoning incidents reported from Vanuatu dating back to the early 17th century. According to Skinner et al. [2], taking into account under-reporting, an estimated 500,000 Pacific islanders might have suffered from CP between 1973 and 2008, with a 60% increase in incidence rates between 1973–1983 and 1998–2008. Such statistics highlight the major threat CP poses in terms of social equity for Pacific Island Countries and Territories (PICTs), communities for whom fish products represent not only a subsistence resource but also a significant source of income [3, 4]. Besides its widely recognized health and socioeconomic impacts, CP also has strong cultural ramifications often overlooked: in some cases, the fear of CP can lead to

a permanent dietary shift among local populations, and even to a disruption in the transmission of traditional subsistence fishing knowledge between generations [3]. In this context, benefiting from effective CP risk monitoring and prevention programs is critical for these communities.

Successful CP risk surveillance depends on the availability of accurate epidemiological data [5], in conjunction with the implementation of environmental monitoring programs. Yet, to date, most PICTs already confronted with CP outbreaks still lack official statistics due to the absence of proper reporting systems, while others not yet affected by this disease are seeking to prepare to face this emerging risk, especially in light of the effects of global change. In this regard, French Polynesia (FP) stands as an exception, as it is one of the few nations having a

research unit devoted to the study of CP since the early 1960s, and an ongoing monitoring program since 2007 [6].

The expertise developed by the Laboratory of Marine Biotoxins of the Louis Malardé Institute (ILM) over the past two decades has led to the development of innovative IT tools, e.g. the dedicated CP websites [7, 8] which provide (i) a wide range of downloadable information on CP, and (ii) allow data collection and access to CP interactive maps, and statistics on CP epidemiology including a list of CP-prone fish species in FP islands. Building on these assets, the Pacific Ciguawatch initiative led by ILM, was launched in 2022 to promote/facilitate the deployment of tailored risk assessment and management programmes in PICTs showing an interest in implementing local CP mitigation strategies.

This initiative relies mainly on the use of the training and CP data sharing e-platform [8], which provides SOPs, video tutorials, technical guides, educational brochures, etc., relating to the sampling and report of the causative microalgae's geographic distribution and biodiversity, as well as improved CP case diagnosis and data collection. A specific module dedicated to the development of tailored community awareness material targeted at the general public, fishers and healthcare worker occupational groups has also been made available.

In 2022–2024, Fiji, Samoa, and Tonga, which have identified CP as a national priority in terms of sea-food safety, food security and nutrition, were trained using the Ciguawatch tools in the frame of the FAO-SAP Technical Cooperation Programme TCP/SAP/3807.

Wallis and Futuna (WF) has had an existing national CP surveillance program since 2015, which helped confirm the presence of *Gambierdiscus* spp. in WF waters, and Futuna as a CP hotspot (85 % of the 122 cases reported between 2018–2024 originated from Futuna). In light of the recent increase in CP incidents in Futuna, local authorities expressed the need to strengthen the country's monitoring and management capacities. In response, a sectorial agreement was signed between the Territory of WF and French Polynesia in November 2023, on the sidelines of the

Fig. 1. Audience of members of the scientific team with her Majesty Lavelua of Wallis (extreme right).

Fig. 2. Location of the eight sampling sites around the islands of (A) Wallis and (B) Futuna.

Fig. 3. Training to the deployment and collection of window screen devices.

52nd Pacific Islands Forum. Hence, from February to September 2024, remote online training sessions were delivered to several Environment, Fisheries, and Health stakeholders. The present article describes the field activities conducted from April 19th to May 5th, 2025 in WF, as a follow-up to this online training.

In many PICTs where customs and traditions are an important part of everyday life, scientific missions involving field activities must receive

the approval of the local king or moral authorities. Hence, no sampling activities could be carried out before an audience with her Majesty Lavelua Patalione Takumasiva Aisake of Wallis, and the two customary chiefs of Sigave and Alo in Futuna (Fig. 1).

In the field, the technical team of the Environment Department of WF was trained in the environmental surveillance of CP through the deployment and collection of window

screen devices over a total of eight sites in WF (Figs. 2–3) using the artificial substrate method described by Tester et al. [9]. These sites were selected based on previous dinoflagellate surveillance data and reports of CP cases collated by the Environment and Health departments. Back at the laboratory, samples were processed and analyzed by microscope observations under the supervision of ILM team (Fig. 4: A,B).

In parallel, several information interventions targeted at healthcare professionals of Sia (Wallis) and Kaleveleve (Futuna) hospitals were conducted in order to improve CP base knowledge, diagnosis and case reporting using a dedicated application via the Ciguawatch platform [10]. In light of the high turnover of the medical staff, all information supports were made available to local health authorities for systematic dissemination to newly arrived staff members. Although CP reporting is not mandatory in WF, the objective of this communication strategy was to alert stakeholders to the importance of accurate CP reporting to support further customized prevention actions. Most importantly, the use of standardized data collection methodologies is meant to ultimately facilitate the comparison of CP status and trends across PICTs.

Finally, younger audiences were not left out, with an educational intervention conducted with two classes of the Malae'fo'ou Elementary School actively involved in a Marine Education Area programme (Fig. 5).

As of now, Health agents can start feeding epidemiological data

Fig. 4. (A) Window screen sample processing and (B) microscope observations for microalgae identification training session.

Fig. 5. (A) School-based intervention in the Elementary school of Mala'efo'ou (Wallis); (B) example of infographic supports used to illustrate CP to a young audience.

onto the Ciguawatch platform. Additionally, window screen samples and fish specimens will be collected by Environment staff, and sent to ILM to characterize *Gambierdiscus* spp. diversity in WF waters by qPCR and for toxicity analyses, respectively. Future activities stipulated in the sectoral agreement signed between WF and FP also include the training of Environment agents in various extraction techniques, as well as internships for WF students at ILM.

The momentum initiated through this regional cooperation programme will hopefully contribute to establish a good inter-agency dynamics and communication, which in turn will benefit the effective surveillance and management of CP incidents in WF.

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Authors

Mireille Chinain, Clémence Gatti Howell & Kévin Henry, Laboratory of Marine Biotoxins, Institut Louis Malardé, UMR SECOPOL, Tahiti, French Polynesia

Ateliana Mangateau, Karine Brunet & Didier Labrousse, Service Territorial de l'Environnement of Wallis and Futuna

Clément Couteaux, Agence de Santé of Wallis and Futuna

Nine Doutroux & Issam Djenidi, Service de l'Agriculture, de la Forêt et de la Pêche of Wallis and Futuna

Email corresponding author: mchinain@ilm.pf

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Mireille Chinain, recipient of the ISSHA Yasumoto Award, poses with her present (Gambierdiscus carving from Prof Takayama) after the 20th ICHA held in Hiroshima. October 2023.